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“DEAD END”

Sirens fade, night stand still;
A story ends against its will.
Behind the films, beneath the lights,
The truth retreats from human sight.

Yellow tape enveloped the scene;
Darkened stain where life had been.
Number was placed where one had breath.
Youthful dreams forcedly robbed by Death.

Beyond the whispers and the wail,
Lies a grief too great to carry.
A mother stands in silent plea,
Clutching what will never be.

For crime is more than law and blame;
It carries loss; it inflicts pain.
But, despite its horror and grim,
We still seek truth despite hurting within.